

Professors and Students Perception on the Implementation of Active Methodologies: A Case Study in the School of Industrial Metallurgical Engineering of Volta Redonda, Brazil

Emerson Carneiro Figueredo ¹, Denise Hirayama¹, Tiago Brandão Costa¹, Ésoly M. Bento dos Santos¹

¹ University Fluminense Federal, Volta Redonda, Brazil

Email: esolysantos@id.uff.br

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Abstract

This study aims to map pedagogical practices in the university context of the School of Industrial Metallurgical Engineering of Volta Redonda (EIMVR), focusing on the principles of active teaching methodologies. The initiative arises amidst a context of the new National Curriculum Guidelines of 2019 and the growing use of Active Learning techniques, which are impacting other universities in Brazil and education in general. We opted for a survey research method, using electronic tools. Through two surveys, one to the faculty and another to the students, with similar questions, in order to compare both points of view on pedagogical practices, issues related to university teaching, and professor-student relationships. These questions were important for analyzing the perception of the use and implementation of active methodologies at EIMVR. The research showed that professors have been applying the fundamentals of active learning in their classes and are open to updating themselves regarding these practices. Results also revealed that professors still do not have a formed opinion on relevant concepts of Active Learning, such as student-centered development and learning. It was also noticeable that, for professors, it is important to value the social side of the student in the pursuit of learning. A relevant difference was observed in some topics, such as dialogue. In the perception of the majority of students, professors are not open to course dialogue, a different situation from the faculty's perception, where the majority claim to be open to this type of conversation. Therefore, it was possible to map differences in the perceptions of the two groups and understand how this dynamic can be improved. In addition, some future actions were proposed that may contribute to the teaching-learning process and mitigate some perceived difficulties in the research.

Keywords: Engineering; Active Methodology; Active Learning; Higher Education.

1 Introduction

The last industrial revolution and globalization have driven scientific and technological advancements in the Brazilian job market, prompting the country to modernize its industrial sector to meet new standards. These advancements also impact higher education institutions, which now need to educate professionals prepared to deal with a market that demands skills such as creativity, leadership, and problem-solving (Furtado, 2013).

This scenario also motivated research by Brazilians such as Professor (Farias 2023), who mapped the profile of faculty members in the Electrical Engineering course at the Federal Institute of Pernambuco. According to his observations on career and faculty profile formation in Brazil, he noted the great need for pedagogical preparation for higher education professionals, who have the responsibility and mission of preparing students for the job market. This finding was corroborated by studies by (Paiva 2015), which, despite addressing a teaching scenario in vocational courses, remains relevant for higher education in Bachelor of Engineering courses in Brazil. Other studies also showed agreement with the analysis by (Farias 2023), demonstrating that many faculty members repeat the same pedagogical practices that were used in their education, despite significant time differences between their education and their teaching role (Dantas, 2011).

Telles also brings these pedagogical considerations to the universe of today's engineer, showing the real need for engineers to achieve some competencies mentioned by (Bazzo & Pereira, 2006) and (Milititsky, 2006) such

as: applying scientific, mathematical, technological, and instrumental knowledge; conceiving, designing, and analyzing systems, projects, and products; ability to identify, formulate, synthesize, and solve problems.

In the same vein of a University Teaching context, (Zabalza 2004, apud in Dantas 2011) discusses a little about the individual character of the development of the work of faculty members within the institution, and that, over the academic trajectory, professionals are forming facing the challenges of personal life and profession.

The problem itself amplifies when there is resistance to participating in faculty training or improvement programs. This turmoil ends up being a reflection of the academic environment itself, which has not valued competent teaching as essential (Dantas, 2011).

The teacher-student binomial has in itself and in its formation complicating factors that make the process more difficult in the pedagogical field. In this context, the present work aims to collect pertinent data through a mapping of the courses of the School of Engineering of Volta Redonda (EEIMVR), in order to understand the profile of the student and the teacher and through a joint analysis, understand the progress of the implementation process of active methodologies by the school.

The theme will be important because it will bring significant results about the pedagogical area of EEIMVR, and will enable the formulation of specific improvements in the field of teaching, which encompasses all courses, with an impact for all students.

2 Materials and Methods

A survey study was conducted using electronic questionnaires to collect quantitative data from a representative sample of teachers and students from EEIMVR. Seventy students from different periods and courses, as well as 89 teachers representing various departments of the school, participated. Google Forms was used as the data collection tool due to its accessibility, ease of question formulation, and automatic graphic resources. The questionnaires were anonymous and included a request for authorization to use the responses in research. Due to its characteristic of visual non-identification, the form did not need to be submitted to the Research Ethics Committee (CEP), in accordance with Art. 1(V) of Resolution No. 510 of April 7, 2016. However, they were sent to the school's management for approval by the director.

Teachers from the EEIMVR Engineering Education Research Group conducted pre-tests of the questionnaire to evaluate the format and understanding of the questions by the respondents. Since the teachers were from the same target audience as the population samples, they were considered qualified for this evaluation. After receiving the questionnaires, the testers provided feedback and suggestions for modifications. Relevant changes were made, resulting in the final version of the questionnaire, which was semi-structured, including closed and open-ended questions. The Likert scale was used to assess the degree of agreement or disagreement of the respondents. Additionally, the questionnaire contained multiple-choice questions.

Two surveys were conducted, one directed to the teachers and another to the students of EEIMVR, aiming to compare their perceptions of the methodologies and pedagogical practices in the institution, especially those related to active learning. The questionnaires addressed sections such as Respondent Profile, Teaching at the University, Pedagogical Strategies, Relationship with Students, and an additional section for teachers about their Area of Education and Performance. Specific terms of active methodologies were not used, opting for questions that indicated the use of these approaches, even if the participants were not familiar with them by name. The survey was disseminated personally, with the assistance of some teachers and QR codes designed to facilitate respondent participation. The data were analyzed in three thematic sections: Teaching Practice and Scientific Research, Importance of Pedagogical Practices, and Relevance of Industrial Experience.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Professors' Profile

The research revealed that the majority of respondents are male (58.8%), while 38.2% are female, with a small portion (2.9%) choosing not to disclose. The male predominance was also noted by the teachers interviewed in another study (Dantas, 2011). This male dominance reflects the historical gender preference in the engineering profession, especially in urban and industrial environments. The predominant age group of the interviewed professors is 30 to 50 years old (79%). Over 90% of the teachers hold a doctorate, suggesting a high level of qualification, possibly related to the requirements for working in public universities in Brazil. Additionally, the research evaluated the pedagogical updating of the teachers, seeking to understand their interest in the continuous improvement of teaching practice, especially regarding the use of active methodologies, which encourage the experimentation of new strategies for more engaging learning. The analysis of teachers' responses regarding their pedagogical updating revealed interesting patterns.

The majority of participants (84%) are undergoing updating processes, either through remote activities (39.4%), frequent readings (36.3%), or in-person events (9.1%). Approximately 12.1% reported being unaware of some of the university's training offerings, while the same proportion (12.1%) showed little interest in pedagogical specialization. These results highlight two issues: lack of information about available courses and disinterest in the pedagogical area, which can exacerbate educational problems, as pointed out by (Dantas 2011). The possible undervaluation of pedagogical updating in university teaching may be linked to the emphasis of teachers on scientific research, to the detriment of teaching. Behrens (1998) suggests that this difficulty in motivating teachers reflects an academic environment that does not value such practices, evidenced by the preference for participation and publications in events and scientific research. The engineering professor has little incentive to engage in events and publications in the educational field.

3.2 Students' Profile

The results showed that 39.4% of respondents are female, a percentage similar to that of the interviewed professors. This indicates that male predominance occurs not only among the faculty but also among the students. Most students (85%) are between 18 and 26 years old. Compared to the professors, these numbers reveal a relatively large generational gap among the respondents.

3.3 Teaching at the University

In order to facilitate understanding, the text was organized into three thematic sections: Teaching Practice and Scientific Research, Importance of Pedagogical Practices, and Relevance of Industrial Experience. Each of these sections examined both the perspective of teachers and that of students. The numbers one to five presented in the following figures represent the degree of agreement of the respondents: 1 - Strongly Disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 - Agree, 5 - Strongly Agree.

a) Teaching Practice and Knowledge of Scientific Research

The results of Figure 1 reflect the opinions of students and teachers on two questions: the relationship between experience time as professor and the quality of classes, and the knowledge about the research conducted by the professors.

Figure 1. a) Teaching Practice and b) Knowledge of professor's research

The majority of professors (60%) value experience time as crucial for teaching, aligning with previous studies (Zabalza, 2004) indicating professional development of teachers through facing challenges, including in the classroom. On the other hand, only 20% of students consider experience teaching time crucial, reflecting different perspectives on experience. While students compare professors to each other, the teaching staff forms their perception based on their own background.

The importance of teacher training and updating is highlighted, as simply adopting a methodology for a long time does not necessarily make it better, and old lesson plans may not be effective due to generational changes (Rocha et al., 2018).

Figure 1b reveals that the majority of students disagree with knowing about teachers' research, indicating little knowledge about their research areas. Integrating scientific research into teaching practice through active methodologies like PBL may encourage teachers to incorporate research elements in the classroom, promoting a deeper understanding of concepts and stimulating students' scientific curiosity.

A suggestion of greater integration of scientific research with teaching at EEIMVR, highlighting the importance of creation of collaborative environments among professors to share experiences and adopt new teaching methodologies. Students' knowledge about teachers' research can foster closer relationships between them, making research areas more known and applied in specific disciplines, in line with National Curriculum Guidelines.

b) Importance of Pedagogical Practices

The results from Figures 2a) and 2b) reveal that both students and professors agree that teachers need to update themselves and consider research in the field of teaching important. Regarding the relationship between research and teaching, illustrated in Figure 2c), the majority of teachers and students do not consider research more important than teaching. However, teachers show greater engagement with research, which may be reflected by incentives since the hiring process and during careers where scientific production is more valued compared to teaching. (Cunha, 2006).

Figure 2. a) Update of pedagogical practices. b) Importance of researching new practices. c) Comparison of research and teaching.

3.4 Used Methodologies

This section addresses the inquiries posed to both groups to identify the use of active teaching-learning methodologies.

The results revealed a variety of methodologies in the classroom, perceived by both students and teachers. The majority of teachers (84.5%) consider their lectures highly participatory, whereas for students (72.5%), this participation is limited. This disparity may be related to the perception of active participation or its frequency. The research did not address the frequency of the use of practices in class, leaving room for a variety of reported experiences. Additionally, it was not assessed whether teachers fully master the methods, their application, and evaluation, which directly influences the results, as discussed by (Ribeiro,2002). Regarding the use of audiovisual resources, the majority of teachers (93.9%) utilize them, but merely providing technology does not guarantee a significant change in learning. It is essential to empower teachers to use these tools effectively and innovatively, which requires continuous pedagogical training to develop skills and effective strategies (Behrens, 2010).

3.5 Pedagogical Practices of Teachers

In this section, an analysis of the use of active methodologies is shown regarding the professor's perception of their role in the teaching-learning process. Figure 3 a) refers to the teacher's perception regarding knowledge transmission, and Figure 3 b) illustrates the teacher's perception regarding Teaching and Learning Assessment.

Figure 3. Professors' perception a) regarding the transmission of knowledge regarding b) Teaching-Learning Assessment.

The results reveal a lack of consensus among teachers, with some maintaining a traditional view of teaching, where the teacher plays a central role in the teaching-learning process, while others recognize the importance of Active Learning centered on the student. Studies, such as Silva et al. (2019), demonstrate better learning outcomes with active methodologies compared to conventional methods. Finally, it is important to highlight that this active learning approach is integrated into the new National Curriculum Guidelines (DCN) for Engineering courses in Brazil, aiming to encourage students to seek their own knowledge and engage in research environments with guidance from the teacher. The results in Figure 3b reveal the perception of assessments. The majority of teachers (60%) agree that assessments should cover the entire content of the discipline to evaluate student assimilation.

It is important to mention the emphasis placed on student competencies by the new National Curriculum Guidelines (DCN's), which propose not only to assess knowledge but also how closely that engineering student approaches the competencies required of a modern engineer. Therefore, it is indispensable for the teacher to consider evaluative methods that check the development of such competencies. Hence, the importance of designing and structuring such methodologies in a and intentional, for greater student learning.

Considering that the relationship between student and professor has a strong influence on the learning process, this part of the research considered the social aspect, student interest, and low performance in evaluations. These points were used to understand the perception of both students and teachers on this aspect. The results regarding the social aspect are presented in Figures 4 a) and b).

Figure 4. a) Knowledge of the students' social situation. b) Knowledge of the students' problems.

About 60% of the professors' respondents partially or fully agree that knowledge of students' social, economic background, and life situation influences learning. The results from the students were more varied, but the majority agree. This contrasts with previous studies (Dantas, 2011), indicating a shift in teachers' perception,

who now value the social aspect of students more. Figure 4 b) shows that the majority consider it important for teachers to know the problems students face. These results reflect coherence and a greater interest from teachers in this theme, with over 80% showing attention to it. Studies by (Gil, 2018) highlight the importance of the teacher-student relationship for learning.

The results regarding low performance on assessments are presented in Figures 5. There is a different perception between students and teachers: students do not believe that teachers are concerned about low performance, while teachers claim to take measures in these cases. The lack of dialogue between teacher and student may explain this discrepancy.

Figure 5. Perception of performance on assessments.

4 Conclusion

The study highlights the importance of professors seeking pedagogical update courses to meet the demands of the university context. According to the results presented, it is clear that many professors are using active methodologies in response to new curricular guidelines. Since it was not evident to the authors what the respondents' initial knowledge of active learning methodologies was, the research used general terms instead of specific nomenclatures like "Project-Based Learning" and "Flipped Classroom." The research indicates that Active Learning is well received by both professors and students, suggesting the continuation of these practices to increase student motivation and interest. A balance between traditional and active methodologies is recommended to improve student engagement. Effective communication between professors and students is highlighted as a crucial element for the development of active methodologies and the improvement of the academic environment. Overall, the results suggest a favorable context for the systematic and structured implementation of active methodologies at EEIMVR. Additionally, professors showed openness to training courses, indicating that even those with less knowledge on the subject recognize that student-centered learning is fundamental for training engineers with the skills required by the current market.

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